

Current issues of Humus science

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An analysis of the nearly 250-year history of the formation and development of the theory of soil humus shows that the most controversial (and therefore relevant at all times) problems in this area of knowledge are the reality of the existence of humic substances as special natural formations, evidence of the specificity of their structure and properties, the reasons for their stability over time, as well as their participation in the implementation of the most important ecosystem functions. The study of soil humus at different levels of its organization for more than 50 years allowed me to develop and substantiate the concept of humus as a natural open system of interconnected humic substances, possessing the properties of self-organization, self-regulation and performing in its entirety a number of integral systemic functions, such as participation in ensuring fertility, forming a soil profile, stability over time, preserving information and others. The main provisions of this concept, considered mainly at the level of humus composition, were first presented in a holistic form in the eighties of the last century (Dergacheva, 1984, 1989). Further study of soil humus as a natural open (dissipative) self-organizing and self-regulating system revealed (Dergacheva, 2018) that humic acids (HA) have the most specific parameters and relatively narrow ranges of variation of quantitative characteristics within different formation conditions. They have a single structural principle, regardless of the source of humification, but differ significantly from each other at the level of quantitative indicators. The close relationships between different quantitative parameters of HA and the climate indicators of local areas of their location, revealed using monofactorial series, made it possible to determine the indicator significance of their main molecular characteristics when assessing the conditions of the natural environment that forms them, the direction and degree of transformation, as well as stability-variability due to a changing natural environment. Thus, H:C in HA reflects the climatic environment of soil formation, changes in functioning conditions; Its value is well preserved over time and can serve as a reliable indicator in **determining** the bioclimatic conditions of the formation of soils of different ages and paleosols. The O:C ratio reflects the textural state of soils and is closely related to their granulometric composition. The H:C–O:C ratio can serve as a reliable indicator of the classification of soils, differences in horizons with different oxidative-reductive conditions of formation and/or the direction of changes under different impacts on soils. Other HA parameters obtained by different independent spectral methods are closely related to the H:C value, as well as to the climatic indicators of their formation (all correlation coefficients are in the range of 0.75–0.95).

The existing working database, which was used in interpreting the HA study materials, currently contains information on the composition and properties of more than ten thousand HA soils of different ages and formation conditions, as well as climatic parameters for almost every local area of their location. The overall assessment of the specificity of the composition, properties and behavior of humic acids in a changing natural and anthropogenic environment makes it possible to consider HA as a matrix that ensures the preservation of the humic substance system, which performs the main important functions in ecosystems and the biosphere as a whole.

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